

An Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment for Developmental Neurotoxicity: Fluoxetine as a Case Study

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Abstract

An *in vitro* battery (IVB) of 17 assays has been developed to screen chemicals for potential developmental neurotoxicity (DNT). This battery leverages new approach methods (NAMs) targeting key neurodevelopmental processes such as neuronal differentiation, migration, synaptogenesis, and myelination. In this presentation, multiple data streams will be combined for a case study compound, fluoxetine, in an Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA). The IATA is designed to provide additional context to DNT IVB data by including QSAR modeling, physiologically based kinetic (PBK) modeling (with *in vitro*-to-*in vivo* extrapolation) and an *in vivo* alternative DNT model using planaria. The integration of PBK modeling is especially important for fluoxetine, which forms an active metabolite (norfluoxetine) that should be considered when estimating fetal exposures. *In vivo* animal and human epidemiology studies from the scientific literature will be reviewed in an effort to better understand the relationship between DNT NAMs and *in vivo* outcomes. This presentation will highlight both the opportunities and challenges of integrating diverse data streams in the application of DNT IVB.